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FORMATION AND DEVELOPMENT OF THE PHILOSOPHY OF
POSITIVISM

Telebaev Gaziz Turysbekovich. Professor
Kazakh National University named after Al-Farabi
Salimov Baxriddin Lutfullaevich.
Associate Professor of Tashkent State Transport University.

Abstract: *The philosophy of positivism occupies an important place in the philosophy of the 20th century (in the sense that positivism is positive). This trend appeared in the middle of the 19th century, and its representatives are John Stewart, Mill Herbert Spencer, August Comtes. According to them, in order to gain knowledge, special sciences should be developed without philosophy. This movement spread widely in Europe in the 30s of the XIX century.*

Key words: *positivism, John Stewart, Mill Herbert Spencer, August Comte.*

Progress comes from nature and society, cooperation between people and people, it is evolutionary. So, revolution is not the only way of development.

We decided not to make big leaps or radical destruction, but to move from one stage to the next, that is, to advance in an evolutionary way. This theoretical conclusion is important for philosophy.

Synergetics mainly relies on the law of relationship between unstable state and stable state, disequilibrium and balance in the process of development. The words "stability" and "unbalance" should not be viewed only from a negative point of view, but their positive aspects should not be forgotten. Instability and stability as a result of regularity and causality, just as the microworld itself is a whole according to the theory of waves and corpuscles, so the existence consists of the mutuality of stability and stability. For this reason, it is impossible to explore the world without any of them.

So, in the 20th century, development was reflected as social and political life, processes of scientific and technical revolution, spiritual and cultural activities, problems of philosophy, sometimes they were revealed negatively, sometimes positively.

The philosophy of positivism occupies an important place in the philosophy of the 20th century (in the sense that positivism is positive). This trend appeared in the middle of the 19th century, and its representatives are John Stewart, Mill Herbert Spencer, August Comtes. According to them, in order to gain knowledge, special sciences should be developed without philosophy. This movement spread widely in Europe in the 30s of the XIX century. For example: Herbert Spencer, one of the great representatives of positivism, worked for 36 years on his 10-volume book called "Synthetic Philosophy". He connected the theory of evolution to social life. He understood the development of personality as the supreme goal of evolution. French philosopher and sociologist Tord Gabriel compared society to chemistry. The cell of society is consciousness. Therefore, he says, the starting point of society is the individual's psyche. Society is the product of the interaction of these individual minds.

According to the French philosopher-sociologist Durk Geim Emile, relying on the natural sciences gives positive results. He promoted the idea of social unity.

The German scientist Tönnis Ferdinand proposed to create "pure" concepts in philosophy. He analyzed the relationship between men in his work "community and society". He opposed the idea of racism. He was an anti-fascist and a democrat. Positivism, which was called bourgeois philosophy in the earlier period, was widespread in Russia later. They called natural sciences positive, i.e. positive or exact sciences. Positivists claimed that philosophy was needed only when natural science was underdeveloped, some sciences were fragmented and could not provide a general idea of the universe, and each science still had many shortcomings. At that time, it really justified itself as a philosophy (philosophy of nature). Because, at that time, philosophers used to imagine the unity and development of the universe based on their imaginations and assumptions. They made up for the shortcomings of the exact sciences. Some of these ideas were later confirmed by scientific discoveries. Some were unconfirmed. According to O. Comte, such a situation is no longer necessary. Natural sciences have strengthened themselves. Natural sciences can explain not only specific areas, but also general aspects, worldview issues. Natural science itself is a philosophy. Philosophy has become useless. In his opinion, philosophy is even harmful to science. Because every researcher of nature who strictly adheres to a certain worldview tries to find what he believes in nature. This seems to prevent scientific research from being objective.

According to them, the main task of philosophy should be to develop a theory of knowledge for naturalists and logic, which is a set of formal rules for discussion and conclusion and their modification. Marxist philosophy opposed this. According to Marxists, a scientist who does not have a worldview cannot be himself. But positivists rejected any philosophy. They were formed as subjective idealists. People recognized the processes and things needed for their experience. They exaggerated the experience. By experience, they understood only the sum of human intuition and perception. They argue that every object, shape, color, taste, smell is a sum, which exists only because of its perception of the subject. With this, positivists pretended to be philosophers of natural science. They wanted to show their connection to scientific discoveries. But it should be noted that they (the positivists) stimulated the development of philosophy and natural sciences, they raised many important problems.

The second stage in the development of positivism was created by E. Max and R. Avenaris. It was carried out under the name of Maximism, and in modern times it has received the name of neopositivism. The science in which Maximism played a leading role in the late 19th and early 20th centuries was physics, and they relied on it. As physics was revolutionized and the old metaphysical concepts of matter, motion, space, time, causation, and the like were completely destroyed, they took advantage of the difficulties that arose. They also claimed that natural science alone can solve the problem of worldview. They say that the task of philosophy is related to the correct assessment of the theory of knowledge. Materialism and idealism were promoted as having limited activity. With this, they tried to show that they are on the third path. They seem to have created a new philosophy. Sometimes they showed themselves to

be neutral in philosophy. According to Marxism, philosophy was partisan two thousand years ago, and will continue to be so. And that was wrong.

Neo-positivists, who are considered to be the next stage of positivism, were formed on the basis of empiricism in the 20s and 30s of the 20th century. Max's disciples are the founders of these currents. They are also called neomaxists. Neopositivists believe that the contradictions between matter and mind, physical state and mental state, materialism and idealism, arise from the willful misuse of words. Therefore, the task of logic is to prevent these contradictions by defining the "symbols" of language. The world of thought, our experience cannot introduce anything new, cannot go beyond human senses. Neopositivists demanded that Machists abandon the word matter itself, while their successors tried to get rid of previous ideas about space, time, and causality using relativity and quantum theories. They did not recognize their objectivity. Neomaxism (neopositivism) was later called logical positivism. They denied the philosophy of mankind and tried to change their philosophy through logical terms. They focused on developing the logic of science. They insisted that all events should be logically analyzed. Calling to abandon philosophical problems in life, they preached that all confusion lies in philosophy. According to R. Carnap, the great representative of logical positivists, the confusion called philosophy should be replaced by the logic of science. Such a normal-terminological, linguistic approach to philosophy was developed by the philosophy called semantic philosophy, growing out of the logical positivism of the 1930s. Semantic philosophers exaggerated the role of language in society. (Semantics is a branch of linguistics that studies the meaning of words and phrases). The theory of knowledge of logical positivists also repeats the theory of knowledge of Machists.

Their representatives are R. Carnap, O. Neurath, G. Reichenbach, Bernard Russell, K. Popper, post positivists T. Kuhn, P. Faierbend. Neopositivism interpreted the place of "symbols" or signs in scientific knowledge. Philosophical ideas about mathematization and formalization of knowledge were presented. They believe that special scientific knowledge is the only science. Neopositivism argued that the task of philosophy is to analyze linguistics. Representatives of neopositivism analyzed the complex areas of logic and linguistics by adapting them to the problems of the present time. In this sense, neopositivism achieved positive results in philosophy. Trying to seriously develop philosophy, they began to recognize that the tasks facing natural science should also be faced by philosophy. The effort to make philosophy positive led to a radical renewal of its branches and departments, which are closely related to natural sciences, mathematics, and technical sciences. Proponents of this doctrine had a great influence on the development of the methodology of logic and other sciences. Neopositivism demands that all ideas and viewpoints put forward in scientific knowledge be checked for their scientificity and truth from the point of view of experience. They want knowledge to be free from fakes. Therefore, they put forward the principle of verification (conviction), which helps the development of philosophical thoughts. Neopositivists developed formal logic in their teaching, created a new type of language analysis that is rapidly becoming formalized. As a result of their (Russell, Carnap, Wittgenstein) teachings, cybernetics, informatics and other fields are developing.

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